

MAELSTROM

MArInE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D1.6

Data Management Plan 3

20/12/2024

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General Information

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History of changes

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable provides an analysis of the main elements of the data management implementation of the project, updating the first MAELSTROM Data Management Plan, following the latest EC guidelines adopted for the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD Pilot). It describes the project policy for data management - i.e. collecting and sharing procedures - including a detailed description of all datasets that have been collected, processed or generated in all Work packages during the course of the MAELSTROM project. It contains all guidelines agreed by partners to allow data to be FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-Usable.

In particular, this document updates the first version of the DMP in the following points:

- a) The MAELSTROM Data Summary, including the list of the project data, has been updated;
- b) The MAELSTROM Data policy and License Agreement has been drafted (Annex I) and a form, the MAELSTROM Data access request form (Annex II) is now available for the data request;
- c) The infrastructure used by MAELSTROM for the data management has been set up to meet the FAIR data principles and it is now described in section 7. A specific internal guide for the Consortium, the MAELSTROM Data Management manual, was prepared to describe the procedure to upload data and metadata (Annex 3).

The deliverable has been prepared with the collaborative work among the Coordinator and the Consortium Partners who are involved in data collection, production and processing. The herein described policy reflects the current state of Consortium agreements regarding data management and is consistent with those referring to the exploitation and protection of results. Nevertheless, it can also be considered as a checklist / guideline for future data collection and exploitation activities.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex issues regarding the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy.

MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) outlines a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions while providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) raises social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

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2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following members:

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3 Aims of the Deliverable

The present Deliverable provides an analysis of the main elements of the data management implementation of the project, updating the MAELSTROM Data Management Plan. The MAELSTROM Data Management Plan 2 describes the data management life cycle for the data collected, processed and/or generated by the MAELSTROM project.

The DMP 2 defines the management strategy of data generated during the project with the purpose to making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR). According to the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, the DMP involves all partners and is supervised by the Data Manager appointed by CNR.

This document includes the Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) section which is dealing with innovation management, establishing the methodology and guidelines for management of innovation within the MAELSTROM Project. The activity is supervised by the Innovation Manager (IM) appointed by ALPHA UK.

3.1 DMP as a checklist

This deliverable can also be considered as a checklist for the future. It is a living document that is expected to mature during the project lifetime and has been and will be updated accordingly. Up this point of the project only slightly changes in the previously described datasets have been observed. Any changes during the last stage of the project will be reported in the last version of the Document.

3.2 Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured following the guideline of H2020 programme on FAIR Data Management Horizon 2020 including the following information:

- Data Management Plan (DMP) guiding principles and strategy
- Data Manager
- QAP and Innovation Manager
- Description of MAELSTROM type of data
- Description of FAIR DATA characteristics including DMP Review Process & data inventory
- Allocation of resources
- Data Security

- Ethical Aspects
- Conclusions

4 Policy for Data Management

The general outline for the project policy for data management (i.e. collecting and sharing procedures), includes the following themes:

- Outline the types of data already generated and / or foreseen to be generated by the project, including the context and procedures behind data generation
- Specify data degree of privacy and confidentiality
- Outline those procedures that will be followed to assess the generated/collected data with respect to their sensitiveness.
- Outline data acquisition plan for the duration of the project.

The European Commission aims to ensure that all Horizon 2020 projects are guided by ethical considerations. Central issue in research ethics is personal data protection, where personal data is information that relates to an identified or identifiable natural person. More specifically, 'identifiable natural person' is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person

Protection of personal identifiable information of European citizens is regulated by GDPR.

In research settings, data protection imposes obligations on researchers to provide participants to project activities (e.g. volunteers, public meeting participants etc.) with detailed information about what will happen to their personal data. It also requires the organisation processing the data, to ensure that the data are properly protected, minimised, and destroyed when no longer needed (Ethics and data protection, by European Commission, DG Research and Innovation).

The DMP and its updated version DPM 2 have been prepared considering the template provided by "Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020" (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf).

The Consortium complies with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).

Procedures implemented for data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction are in line with EU standards as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

5 Roles and responsibilities

5.1 Data manager (DM)

The DM, Dr Valentina Grande, appointed by CNR, coordinates the data management of the Project to assure usability, accountability and quality of the data and valorise it, either by using it for other market applications when possible and relevant or by making them open to the scientific community. The DM thus leads the DMP and the participation of MAELSTROM in the Open Research Data Pilot, implementing and overseeing the DMP methodology to assure good data management and valorisation.

5.2 Quality Assurance Plan

The Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) is defined by the structures and through the procedures described in details in the Deliverables D1.1 Set up of project structures and D1.2 MAELSTROM Project Handbook:

- the MAELSTROM governance structure, communication flows and methods;
- the procedure for internal reporting from task level to General Assembly level;
- the procedure for internal peer review of deliverables and periodic reports; Consortium contact information and responsible/participants from General Assembly to Task level;
- project templates, conflict resolution procedures and risk management procedures.

These structures, procedures and workflows are crucial to ensure the quality of the products of the MAELSTROM project.

5.3 Innovation manager (IM)

The innovation management process is governed by the IM, Elizabeth A. Nerantzis (ALPHA UK) and it is implemented by adopting a hybrid research and innovation

methodology. The IM iteratively considers the evolution of products and market demands, the business strategies of the enterprises present in the Consortium, and the results achieved to adjust Project objectives and requirements, specifying the innovations on which MAELSTROM should focus more and identifying exploitation potentials. The IM coordinates the Project activities that paves the way for innovation and possible market uptake. She is responsible for the innovation management and exploitation plan within the Project and follows up on this plan, coordinating exploitation activities across partners.

6 MAELSTROM Data Summary

6.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The MAELSTROM Data Management Plan (DMP) and its updated version DMP 2 aim to provide a strategy for managing data generated and collected during the project and to optimise access to and re-use of research data. Data generated during the project are related to the different MAELSTROM objectives as specified in the Grant Agreement and summarized below:

- **Objective 1** "Assessing the effectiveness and impact of ML removal on coastal marine ecosystems". Data collected during the ecosystem assessment activities performed in the Italian and Portuguese demo sites in the framework of the WP2, including both data available from literature and generated from field surveys.
- **Objective 2** "ML Removal from seabed and both lower and upper water column". Data collected for the development of the technologies and during the removal activities on ML quantity and typology, collected in the framework of WP3, WP4 and WP5.
- **Objective 3** "Feeding circular economy and sustainability consists of compiling raw data provided by stakeholders in the format of agreed metrics". Data collected involving diversified players in the plastic value chain and deploying a mix of ML treating technologies made of physical, chemical solutions, in the framework of WP6 activities.
- **Objective 4** "Clustering of blue technologies for joint plastic strategy-oriented efforts". Data collected from stakeholders during the coordination and networking activities within projects under the same topic, as well as projects selected under other topics in H2020 for the reduction, removal and

sustainable management of ML in the coastal areas, collected in the framework of WP7.

- **Objective 5** “Engaging society for ML prevention, removal and circular economy”. The data produced in the framework of WP8 contribute to the stakeholder engagement in adopting the MAELSTROM technologies. Data generated during the societal engagement activities in the framework of WP9: citizens and local administrations have been engaged in order to raise their awareness about the ML issue also through specific dissemination campaigns, including participatory and large scale clean up.

6.2 What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

All MAELSTROM datasets are reported in the current section. The project brings together multiple types of data with multiple levels of dissemination. For readability purposes, the following data tables have been divided via work packages. A brief description of each work package is included to correctly focus the theme and related data.

The different types of data produced by the project can be grouped across the following categories:

- **Documentation material:** transcripts and agendas of meetings, reports, non-structured data;
- **In situ data:** environmental data, marine litter data, cleaning devices operational data, etc.;
- **Simulation data:** 3D hydrodynamic model, 3D marine litter transport model, etc.;
- **Experimental data:** sample lab analysis, marine litter lab analysis data, analysis of the recycled material and recycling process, etc.;
- **Compiled data:** i.e., marine litter sources in the demo sites, marine litter data from literature, stakeholder database, etc.

The tables have been organized as follows. For each row we have the following **mandatory information** (*in green*):

- **Dataset Name:** the name of the dataset
- **Data Type:** see previous categorization
- **Data Format:** e.g. Jpeg, TIFF, pdf
- **Data Provider:** e.g. Copernicus, EMODnet, etc.
- **Data source:** e.g. Sentinel-1

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- **Data Access rights:** only for internal usage, public, etc.
- **Data size classes:** e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1 GB, > 1GB

Whenever available or feasible, we also collect this optional information (in orange):

- Spatial resolution (if applicable)
- Temporal resolution (if applicable)
- Temporal coverage available
- Data Availability
- Metadata Available
- Standards applied

6.3 Data for Work Package 1

Being the MAELSTROM project coordination and management work package, this WP mainly collects documentation materials such as meeting recordings, minutes and reports.

Table 1 MAELSTROM Data Types for WPI

Data set	Data description	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes	Data Access Rights	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability	Metadata available	Standards applied
Recordings of meetings	recording of the teleconferences, webinars, and discussions held among the consortium members	multimedia	mp4	CNR	Webex / Teams	>1 GB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	new data	No	As defined in the CA and WP1 and WP10 Deliverables
Minutes of meetings	transcript of meeting discussions	documents	doc	CNR	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	No	As defined in the CA and WP1 and WP10 Deliverables
Agendas of meetings		documents	doc, pdf	CNR	n/a	< 100 MB	open	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	No	As defined in the CA and WP1 and WP10 Deliverables
Public Deliverables	Reports for the EU Commission as defined in the GA	documents	doc, pdf	CNR	n/a	< 100 MB	open	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	No	As defined in the CA and WP1 and WP10 Deliverables
Restricted Deliverables	Reports for the EU Commission as defined in the GA	documents	doc, pdf	CNR	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	No	As defined in the CA and WP1 and WP10 Deliverables

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6.4 Data for Work Package 2

The work package research activities are assessing ML pollution and ecosystem state in demo sites both PRIOR and AFTER the implementation of MAELSTROM remediation technologies, thus measuring the latter's impact on marine ecosystems and local economies. To carry out these activities, a consistent number of scientific datasets has been and will be collected. They are summarized in the next four tables:

Table 2 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP2 (1 of 2)

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes	Data Access Rights	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability	Metadata available	Standards applied
MS/PAN images	EO	GeoTIFF	CNR	Worldview2/3	>10 GB	internal use	MS:1.2-2m, PAN:0.3-0.52m		2012-2016	existing data	yes	ORStandard2 A
Multibeam bathymetry	in-situ	XYZ	CNR	Multibeam system EM2040 D-C	>1 GB	Available on request	0.05-0.5 m		2013-2020	existing data	yes	NO IHO S-44
Backscatter/ Seafloor imagery	in-situ	GeoTIFF	CNR	MBES	>1 GB	Available on request	0.05-0.5 m		2013-2021	existing data	yes	
Drop Frames Video transects	in-situ	mp4	CNR	Drop fram with Go Pro camera	>1GB	Available on request	1 shot per second		2020	existing data	yes	
Habitat data groundtruth data	in-situ	shapefiles	CNR	Grabs (Van Veen, Ponar), Dives, drop cameras	<100 MB	Available on request	points and a few transects		2013 - 2020	existing data	yes	
Hydrodynamic model data	model	netCDF	CNR	SHYFEM model	>1 GB	Available on request	> 10 m	monthly/annual averages	2014	existing data	yes	
Multibeam bathymetry	in-situ	XYZ	CNR	Multibeam systems including EM2040DC and R2sonic	>1 GB	Available on request	0.05-0.5 m		2021-2023	new data	yes	NO IHO S-44
Macrolitter seafloor distribution	in-situ	shapefiles,csv	CNR	MBES	<100 MB	Available on request	0.05-0.5 m		2021-2023	new data	yes	
Macrolitter watercolumn distribution	in-situ	shapefiles,csv	CNR	MBES	<100 MB	Available on request	0.05-0.5 m		2021-2023	new data	yes	
Backscatter/ Seafloor imagery	in-situ	GeoTIFF	CNR	MBES	>1 GB	Available on request	0.05-0.5 m		2013-2021	new data	yes	
Drop Frames Video transects	in-situ	mp4	CNR	Drop fram with Go Pro;	>1GB	internal use	1 shot per second		2022-2024	new data	yes	
Habitat data groundtruth data	in-situ	shapefiles	CNR	Grabs (Van Veen, Ponar), Dives, drop cameras	<100 MB	internal use	points / transects		2022-2024	new data	yes	
Hydrodynamic model data	model	netCDF	CNR	SHYFEM model	>1 GB	internal use	> 10 m	monthly/annual averages	to be evaluated	new data	yes	
Environmental data (Temperature; Salinity, Currents)	in-situ	shapefiles	CNR	ADCP, CTD	<100 MB	open	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	
Benthic community matrices (abundance, biomass, coverage, etc.)	in-situ	csv	CNR	field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines
Fish community matrices (abundance, biomass, etc.)	in-situ	csv	CNR	field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines
Microplastic abundances on bioindicator species	in-situ	csv	CNR	field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	
Microplastic abundances on sediments	in-situ	csv	CNR	Grab sampler	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	JPI Ocean
Sediment granulometry	in-situ	csv	CNR	Grab sampler	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	
Floating microplastics	in-situ	csv	CNR	Manta trawl	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2022-2024	new data	yes	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
Floating microplastics (> 20 micron)						Available on request	points / transects	every six months	2023-2024	new data	yes	
Beach litter	in-situ	csv	VLPF	field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	100m	occasional	2021-2023	new data	yes	Marine Strategy Framework Directive

Table 3 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP2 (2 of 2)

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes	Data Access Rights	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability	Metadata available	Standards applied
Environmental data (abiotic factors: temperature, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen, depth, total suspended solids, total dissolved solids)	in-situ	csv	CIIMAR	Multiparametric probe - field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + 4 periods after BB implementation	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines for Portugal
Environmental data (biotic factors: chlorophyll a concentration, phytoplankton diversity and abundance)	laboratory	csv	CIIMAR	Spectrofotometry and Optic observations- field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + 4 periods after BB implementation	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines for Portugal
Benthic community matrices (abundance, diversity, biotic indexes)	laboratory	csv	CIIMAR	Grab Van Veen - field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + 4 periods after BB implementation	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines for Portugal
Fish community matrices (diversity)	in-situ	csv	CIIMAR	field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + 4 periods after BB implementation	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines for Portugal
Prioritary substances (metals, nutrients, PAHs)	in-situ	csv	CIIMAR	Chemical Analytic data - field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + 4 periods after BB implementation	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	Water Framework Directive Guidelines for Portugal
Marine Litter	in-situ	csv	CIIMAR	field survey	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + after BB implementation every months	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	
Floating microplastics	in-situ	csv	CIIMAR	Plankton net	<100 MB	Available on request	points / transects	two period before BB implementation + 4 periods after BB implementation	2021 + 2022-2024	new data	yes	
Hydrodynamic model data	model	dat	CIIMAR	Delft3D model	>1 GB	Available on request	> 10 m	key scenarios	key scenarios	new data	yes	
Hydrological model data	model	dat	Deltares	W-Flow model	>1 GB	Available on request	Hydrographic basin	key scenarios	key scenarios	new data	yes	

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6.5 Data for Work Package 3

Work Package 3 deals with the creation, implementation and testing of the seabed cleaning robotic platform. Datasets are composed mainly by technical data, video datasets, software and hardware requirement documents to contribute to the design of the platform and its function.

Table 4 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP3

						e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1 GB, (internally, open...)					Existing data or newly generated		
Recordings of meetings	recording of the teleconferences, webinars, and discussions held among the consortium members	multimedia	mp4	TECNALIA	teams	>1 GB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	new data	no	
Minutes of meetings	transcript of meeting discussions	text	doc	TECNALIA & LIRMM-CNRS	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Requirements for the seabed cleaning platform design	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	TECNALIA & LIRMM-CNRS	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Design and selection of components that integrate the seabed cleaning platform	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	TECNALIA & LIRMM-CNRS & ST Venice	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Selection and location of sensors	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	LIRMM-CNRS & TECNALIA	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Underwater perception, Cable robot teleoperated control and preliminary testing	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	LIRMM-CNRS & TECNALIA	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Validation of seabed cleaning platform	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	ST Venice & TEC	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Cable robot control system improvement - shared autonomy to improve ergonomics of the pilot station	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	LIRMM- CNRS	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
Cable robot control system improvement – machine learning for autonomous cleaning of the seabed	info agreed by partners	text	ppt, doc	LIRMM-CNRS	n/a	< 100 MB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2025	new data	no	
T3.6 : A dataset for training of the machine learning algorithm will be generated based on the human operator work which select litters to collect by clicking on the images.	Image/video database	multimedia	jpg, mpeg or equivalent	LIRMM-CNRS	WP3 participants	100 MB to 1GB, > 1 GB	internal use first for research, then open in the frame of WP7	camera resolution (at least 1080p)	if video 25-50 Hz to be defined	2021-2025	new data	labels associated to the images/frames (position, bounding box and identification of the litter)	standard format

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6.6 Data for Work Package 4

As for WP3, Work Package 4 is focused on the technology for the water column and surface plastics collection in the Ave River (Northern Portugal). The system implemented makes use of the Great Bubble barrier technology. In this light, the work package has collected the environmental data (bathymetry, currents, etc.) needed to design and put in place the Bubble Barrier.

Table 5 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP4

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1 GB, > 1GB	Data Access Rights (internally, open...)	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability Existing data or newly generated during MAELSTROM	Metadata available	Standards applied
Bathymetric survey	in-situ	csv	TGBB	single-beam sonar combined with dual-frequency differential high-precision GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System)	>1 GB	open	one location + tracks	1 sounding per second along tracks		new	no	
Temperature and salinity Amsterdam	in-situ	csv	Deltares	CTD at fixed location collected by AquaVision for Deltares	<100 MB	open	one location	1 minute	1 week	new	yes	
Flow velocity Amsterdam	in-situ	csv (and raw data)	Deltares	ADCP collected by AquaVision for Deltares	>1 GB	open	one location + tracks	1 minute	1 week	new	yes	
List of amsterdam litter counted per category	in-situ	XLS list	Deltares	Counting from sorting the litter by the Schone rivieren NGOs	<100 MB	internal until end of project	one location	Every 2 to 4 days	1 week	new	yes	
Flow velocity Ave estuary	in-situ	csv (and raw data)	CIIMAR	Aquadopp Profiler 600 kHz - Nortek, ADCP data collected in the Ave estuary	>1 GB	open	one location	1 minute	1 week	new	no	
Salinity and temperature in Ave estuary	in-situ	csv	TGBB	CTD at fixed location and CTD probe collected by AquaVision for Deltares	100 MB	open	one location		points/transect	new	no	

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6.7 Data for Work Package 5

Aim of this WP is to apply the remediation technologies – MAELSTROM Automated Seabed Cleaning Platform and MAELSTROM Great Bubble Barrier – deployed at demo sites – respectively Venice and Ave River - to fully test their functionalities, operational capacities and cleaning effectiveness. The data include the amount and categories of litter collected and the data related to the technologies' operations.

Table 6 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP5

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1 GB, > 1GB	Data Access Rights (internally, open...)	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability Existing data or newly generated	Metadata available	Standards applied
Seabed Cleaning area data	geospatial data	shapefiles	CNR/ST	ArcGIS produced maps of cleaned areas in Venice Demo Sites	<100 MB	open	areas and cable robot transects	Once a year	2022-2023	new data	yes	
Seabed Cleaning operation location data	in-situ	GPS data	ST/Tecnia	Trimble RTK GPS of the platform and cable robot location	<100 MB	open	areas and cable robot transects	Once a year	2022-2023	new data	yes	
Amount and categories of the removed marine litter	in-situ	xls	CNR	visual analysis of collected litter in the Venice area	<100 MB	open	multiple locations in the Venice area	daily during cleaning operation	2022-2023	new data	yes	MSFD categories
bubble barrier operational data	in-situ	xls	TGBB	manually recorded data about the bubble barrier operations	<100 MB	internal use	n/a	weekly	2022-2024	new data	yes	
Amount and categories of the removed marine litter	analysis of collected litter	xls	CIIMAR	Ave estuary	<100 MB	open	one location	seasonally	2022-2024	new data	yes	OSPAR categories
Collect historical data	analysis of collected literature	file	CIIMAR	Ave estuary	>100 MB	open	one location		2021-2024	existing data	yes	scientific literature

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6.8 Data for Work Package 6

The goal of this WP is to consolidate and deliver a new set of integrated solutions to manage and implement circular economy for the marine litter removed from the coastal areas during the project activities.

Table 7 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP6

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes	Data Access Rights (internally, open...)	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability Existing data or newly generated during MAELSTROM	Metadata available	Standards applied
Data collected during the beach monitoring activities	Amount and categories of the removed marine litter	xls	VLPF / GEES	MAELSTROM app	<100 MB	open	100 m	Yearly	2021 - 2024	New data	Yes	EMODnet chemistry
Data on recycle material	Type of materials and their amount of the recycled marine litter	xls	GEES	MAELSTROM app	<100 MB	open	N/A	Yearly	2021 - 2023	New data	Yes	
Data collection during pyrolysis process	experimental	SQL-database	MAKEEN	Transmitters on valves, temp & pressure gauges, scales, entered information, Automatically logged data, process parameters, qty and quality input materials, qty each output material, process progress parameters	>10 GB	Internal	N/A	N/A	2022-2024	New data	No	
Data collection during pyrolysis process, initial tests	experimental	.xls	MAKEEN	Displays on thermometers, scales, flow gauges, information about input material quality, visual observations, Manually logged data, process parameters, qty and quality input materials, qty each output material, process progress parameters	<100 MB	Internal	N/A	N/A	2021(-2024 if necessary with more initial tests)	Newly generated	No	
Material analysis reports	experimental	.pdf	Analysis companies requested by MAKEEN	Lab equipment, Analysis reports from analysis companies about ingredients/characteristics of oil or gas samples provided for analysis	<100 MB	Internal	N/A	N/A	2022-2024	Newly generated	No	
Dataset of images of marine litter plastics for sorting	images	.jpg	Tecnalia	cameras	>1Gb	Internal	N/A	N/A		Newly generated	No	
LCA results	documents	.doc	Tecnalia	datasheet of components used in the robots	<100 MB	Internal	N/A	N/A		Newly generated	No	
recycled thermoplastics composites characterization report	report	.doc	Tecnalia	Lab equipment	<100 MB	Internal	N/A	N/A		Newly generated	No	

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6.9 Data for Work Package 7

WP7 activities can be summarized as networking activities. Therefore, together with the typical networking tools, the Forum Data Base is the main dataset created in the frame of these activities.

Table 8 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP7

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1	Data Access Rights (internally, open...)	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability Existing data or newly	Metadata available	Standards applied
Forum database	compiled	xls	CIIMAR/CIMA	MAELSTROM online platform	< 100 MB	open	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	Existing data	no	privacy policy
Stakeholders Mapping	Database	Excel	CIIMAR	Institutional databases, Project websites	<100 MB	Internally	Europe	n/a	2021-2024	Existing data or newly generated during MAELSTROM	n/a	privacy policy
Interative Forum	Online platform	Website	CIIMAR, CIMA	Forum Website	100 MB to 1GB	Open (after registration)	Europe	n/a	2021-2024	new data	n/a	privacy policy
Thematic working group on ML and Plastic Strategy	Database, Report	Docx, PDF	CIIMAR		101 MB to 1GB	Public	Europe	n/a	2021-2024	new data	n/a	privacy policy
Forum Webinars	Recording of the webinars	mp4	CIIMAR, CIMA	Zoom platform	>1 GB	internal use	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	new data	n/a	privacy policy
Best Practices Sheets Database	Database and Handbook	Docx, PDF	CIIMAR		100 MB to 1GB	Public	Europe	n/a	2021-2024	new data	n/a	privacy policy
Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions	Report	Docx, PDF	CIMA		101 MB to 1GB	Public	Europe	n/a	2021-2024	new data	n/a	privacy policy
Unified Reports on Side- events at the Business2Sea and at the International Venice Boat Show	Report	Docx, PDF	VLFP		102 MB to 1GB	Public	Europe	n/a	2021-2024	new data	n/a	privacy policy

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6.10 Data for Work Package 8

Work Package 8 is at the core of MAELSTROM business plan creation. In this light, it is useful to recap its activities to understand which kind of data will be produced and collected. WP8 will:

- Estimate the cost-effectiveness of alternative ML reduction technologies;
- Identify drivers and barriers behind current legal and policy frameworks;
- Examine stakeholder acceptance and public preferences for alternative ML reduction technologies;
- Design novel business model and assess the economic feasibility of upscaling and replication of innovative ML reduction technologies in different EU regions;
- Synthesis and integrated assessment of the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the new technologies.

Table 9 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP8

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data Access Rights (internally, open...)	Data size classes e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB to 1 GB, > 1GB	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability Existing data or newly generated during	Metadata available	Standards applied	Analysis	Tools	Future data
Definition a significant case for the CBA and collection of information via desk research and interviews with stakeholders during MAELSTROM demos	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	Existing	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Desk analysis and interviews	
Main costs/ damages related to marine pollution and running costs (Opex)/ investments (Capex) related to system adoption	Unstructured	.doc, .exl	ALPHA	ALPHA know-how	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	Existing	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	One to one interviews/input collection and desk analysis when needed	Quantitative economic data
Monetization of economic and social benefits data brought by MAELSTROM	Unstructured	.doc, .exl	ALPHA	ALPHA know-how	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	One to one interviews/input collection and desk analysis when needed	Quantitative economic data
Market analysis data to identify market segmentation, market trends	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA	Fragmented. Sources will be presented in related deliverables	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	Existing	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Desk analysis and interviews	
Competitive environment assessment data to map main competing solutions and main stakeholders	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA	Fragmented. Sources will be presented in related deliverables	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	Existing	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Desk analysis and interviews	
Data to draft the SWOT (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats) and barriers to entry for MAELSTROM	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA	Fragmented. Sources will be presented in related deliverables	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Desk analysis and interviews	
Data for Preliminary business model(s) definition	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA + Consortium	Fragmented. Sources will be presented in related deliverables	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Descriptive analysis		
Data for Pricing strategy (considering potential users' desired data and constraints)	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA	Fragmented. Consortium know-how	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Descriptive analysis	Interviews and business strategy tools	
Overall Business Plan definition quantifying key assumptions (incl. pricing, market share, CAPEX, OPEX...), over a 5 to 10 years period, to obtain a long-term cash-flow prediction	Unstructured	.doc, pdf	ALPHA + Consortium	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Input collection from partners and business strategy tools	Quantitative economic data
Risk analysis data and information in relation to MAELSTROM uptake and identify main actions to avoid/ mitigate them	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA + Consortium	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Risk assessment tools	
Implementation roadmap: key strategies and drivers for the exploitation activities and solution adoption (from both a consortium and individual point of view).	Unstructured	.doc	ALPHA + Consortium	ALPHA know-how based on Consortium partner contributions	Internal	<100 MB	n/a	n/a	n/a	New data	no		Aggregated data analysis; Descriptive analysis	Input collection from partners and business strategy tools	

6.11 Data for Work Package 9

WP 9 delivers and produces standard dissemination materials.

Table 10 MAELSTROM Data Types for WP9

Data summary	Data type	Data Format	Provider	Data Source	Data size classes	Data Access Rights	Spatial resolution	Temporal resolution	Temporal Coverage available	Data Availability	Metadata available	Standards applied
					e.g. < 100 MB, 100 MB	(internally, open...)				Existing data or		
Minutes of communication meetings	Transcript of communication meeting decisions	.doc	CIMA	N/A	<100 MB	Internal	N/A	monthly	2021-2024	new data	No	
Project videos	videos	mp4	CIMA		> 1 GB	open	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	new data	No	privacy policy signed
Project Graphic Kit	Logos, ppt, graphics	ppt, jpeg, png, svg	CIMA	Graphic software ?	< 1 GB	open	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	new data	No	privacy policy signed
Promotional material	Leaflets, newsletters, etc	doc, pdf	CIMA		< 1 GB	open	n/a	n/a	2021-2024	new data	No	privacy policy signed

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6.12 Will you re-use any existing data and how?

MAELSTROM Project capitalizes on already existing data, integrating them with new data collected and generated through the activities of the project. In particular, the main data capitalised during the activities are listed below:

- Literature review at International, European and national level;
- Academic and 'grey' literature;
- Policy documents and guidance;
- Existing datasets at European and regional levels (e.g., data from COPERNICUS, EMODnet);
- Published business strategies;
- Images and map of studied areas;
- Existing data on policies and policy processes that are available at European, national and (in some cases) regional level;
- Social and news media.

6.13 What is the origin of the data?

The origin of the data can be classified in three categories:

- project partners, affiliated entities and other participants;
- already existing database, freely accessible through the web;
- field surveys;
- laboratory activities;
- technological test.

6.14 What is the expected size of the data?

The MAELSTROM Project expects to manage digital data for about 4 TB.

6.15 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

The data produced in the framework of the MAELSTROM project has been and will be beneficial to a variety of stakeholders including: local administrations, policy makers, private investors and supply chain companies, technology developers, environmental agencies. Information gathered will help identify challenges in the specific areas covered by the Project and serve as an input for policy design at national and European level (i.e. Marine Strategy Framework Directive, Water Framework Directive, Waste Management Directive). Moreover, the data has been and will be useful to the scientific community through scientific production (publications, patents, etc.). Finally, the data has been and will be disseminated to the wider public and

citizen to raise awareness about the marine litter and possible actions to be taken to tackle this issue.

7 MAELSTROM FAIR Data Principles

The “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” [2] guides Horizon 2020 beneficiaries to make their research data **Findable, Accessible Interoperable and Re-usable** (FAIR). This is a required concept (so-called FAIR data principle) by EU-Projects. It should support the exchange of scientific data and lead to knowledge discovery and innovation. The FAIR data approach is described by the acronym:

Table 11 Definition of FAIR data

Definition	Meaning
<i>Findable</i>	Clear naming and versioning of (meta-) data, use of search keywords and DOI
<i>Accessible</i>	Specification of how data are made available and what tools are needed to access data
<i>Interoperable</i>	Use of standards and vocabularies for (meta-)data and datatypes
<i>Reusable</i>	Specification of when - and for which duration - data are made available, licensing of data

Given that (partial) data to be gathered during the project could be used to identify individuals and/or business entities, before making any data public, compliance with EU 2016/679 [3] regulation must be checked. Moreover, taking into consideration that the project may have as its target to gather data that are private, sensitive or relevant to security, each specific category of data needs to be assessed before deciding if it can be public or not. Finally, the effort spent for data assessment should be reasonable compared to the foreseen value of the FAIR data.

The infrastructure used by MAELSTROM for the data management meets the FAIR data principles supporting the exchange of scientific data and leading to knowledge, discovery and innovation. It consists of **three main components**:

1. **NAS repository** for research data storage with cloud functionalities: the system consists in a NAS-QNAP (Network Attached Storage - Quality Network Appliance Provider) that is a storage device with QTS as operating system and myQNAPcloud for the remote access. The NAS repository allows the data providers to store the data in a file system. The Cloud component permits to access the system by browser (https protocol) without the use of USB flash

drivers or Hard Disk using personal credentials (**authentications**). The file system ensures the coherence of final documents and files available 7 days/week and 24h/day except during blocking incident, after which the service can be re-established within few hours. It is systematically structured to permit a multi-level data access according to the user access rights and the permits on the folders (**authorization**). The system allows the data provider to associate URL and password to the digital resource to be used for the sharing. The URL will be included in the metadata record making the data accessible according to its specific data policy. The NAS is stored in CNR-ISMAR based in Bologna with a mirror in a separate location to avoid loss of data, and it substitutes the SeedsDMS platform and the owncloud to store documents and files.

2. **Metadata catalogue** for research data discovery and preservation: the Metadata Catalogue is implemented using the open source software GeoNetwork for the management of digital resources. It represents an organized collection point for the data, products, services produced by the MAELSTROM Project, with the aim to share and exchange information about the data presence, access mode, re-usability, history, and point of contact. The data provider uses the standard **ISO1911539** for spatial datasets, **ISO 19115-2** for Imagery and gridded data, **ISO19119** for Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) web services, **Dublin Core** for non-spatial resource (such as physical sample, web applications, tables, maps and figures). The GeoNetwork describes the entire set of data and represents a unified user interface for searching and exploring metadata in the web.
3. **RoHub platform** for the sharing of the entire research data life cycle and the reuse of scientific results: the ROHub platform enables the management, sharing and preservation of research artefacts as a single information unit through the Research Object (RO) concept and model. ROHub supports scientists and related stakeholders throughout the research lifecycle to create and maintain high-quality ROs that can be interpreted and potentially reproduced. The MAELSTROM Project is using ROs as single digital aggregation entity, to formalize, share and preserve datasets, research products and procedures. ROHub provides access control and publication of ROs including assignment of **DOIs**, as well monitoring and preservation of ROs to ensure that they will remain accessible and re-usable. ROHub is a service in

the **EOSC portfolio** classified as data aggregator and integrator, accessible at the link: https://search.marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/search/service?q=*
The EOSC Service Catalogue is registered as repository in **OpenAIRE**.

Figure 1. Sketch of the infrastructure used by the MAELSTROM Project for data management.

7.1 Making Data Findable

Besides the naming convention, the “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” also propose to have DOI for the data generated during the project. Consequently, the project uses the ISMAR metadata catalogue and RoHub platform (Annex III) to fulfil that requirement. All datasets gathered during the Project are described into the GeoNetwork metadata catalogue using specific standards: ISO10115 for spatial data and Dublin Core for other entities (such as physical samples and documents). Through the GeoNetwork metadata catalogue, partners can assign a persistent identifier (PID), a global unique identifier (GUID), and a (Digital Object Identifier, DOI) to the metadata forms describing datasets and products. The metadata richness is guaranteed by the inclusion in the GeoNetwork forms of all the items considered mandatory (ISO and INSPIRE rules), and by a validation process provided by the catalogue to evaluate the degree of the form completion.

RoHub is a free of charge, open data repository implemented by the HORIZON Projects EVR-EST (Grant agreement ID: 674907) and RELIANCE (Grant agreement ID: 101017501). RoHub is a Research Object (RO) management platform supporting the preservation and lifecycle management of scientific investigations, research campaigns and operational processes. Using RO, scientists can manage and preserve their research work, share it and make it available for publishing, promoting data re-use within EU but also all over the world. Relevant **products** produced by the MAELSTROM Project have been and will be incapsulated in a RO and published into RoHub, where it is possible to associate a DOI. Moreover, the RO are also harvested by OESC and findable through the EOSC Marketplace resources (<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu>), increasing the discoverability of the gathered data made publicly available by MAELSTROM. RoHub offers also the capability, in case the consortium decides so, to restrict data access for a specific group of users (or the public) for a fixed period of time.

7.2 Making Data Accessible

Another important part of the FAIR data principle is to make the data Accessible (FAIR) to the project partners and, when possible, also to other researchers and to the public. Especially, the project aims to make data as open as possible and as closed as necessary. In particular, the partners disseminate data that could potentially be of value for various external parties but at the same time the confidentiality and the privacy of the internally involved parties is not harmed.

In order to achieve the above targets, MAELSTROM project uses the Cloud storage and the GeoNetWork metadata catalogue. Metadata include elements containing all human-readable information to access the data: Resource constraints, Legal constraints and Contact for the resource. Metadata can be accessed and downloaded through the GeoNetwork user interface. If the license of the data is open, the requester can directly access the data by clicking on a link in the relative metadata form; while if the data are password protected, the requester can send an e-mail to the metadata owner/point of contact, or call by telephone to receive instructions. The data links are managed using cloud storage (NAS-QNAP) where the data provider can store the digital resources obtaining a free or password-protected URL (Uniform Resource Locator) to be included in the metadata record. The data provider is free to manage the data requests by himself, using the cloud storage supporting authentication and authorisation. If it is decided that data cannot be publicly shared (or there is a need for sharing restrictions), a justification is provided.

Data that have been and will be collected and are intended to be made available on a public platform must bear a broadcasting authorization by the operator of the site of origin. This requisite is necessary to guarantee any confidentiality and risk of fraudulent use of this data in a competitive context. This is also applicable for data issued from industrial captors, and all pictures and videos.

Data are and will remain accessible to partners on the cloud storage and to general public through the metadata catalogue. Metadata records are guaranteed to remain accessible after data is no longer available, and the status of the data is described in the metadata element Lineage.

7.3 Making Data Interoperable

Making data Interoperable (FAIR) can be achieved by using suitable standards for data and metadata creation while making use of appropriate vocabularies (e.g. for providing search keywords). Especially for the metadata, MAELSTROM adopts the Dublin Core Metadata standard which ensures that the data meet traditional quality and consistency standards while they remain interoperable with other data sources at the same time. The standard includes fifteen elements that introduce a vocabulary of concepts with natural-language definitions that can be converted into machine-readable open formats such as XML, HTML, etc.; hence being processable. The vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard can be found in the following table

Table 12 The vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard

No	Element	Element definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.
3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.
12	Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
13	Relation	A reference to a related resource.
14	Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource.
15	Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.

Metadata in GeoNetwork are readable and thus interoperable for machines without any requirements thanks to the usage of standards. Meta(data) can be connected to other online resources through links to people (ORCIDs), scientific papers (DOIs), projects (webpages), or other meta(data) catalogues. In addition, metadata records can be connected to other digital objects described in the GeoNetwork through the element "Associated resources" defining also the role of the relationship (parent, service, source dataset, source catalogue, other resource).

7.4. Making Data Re-Usable

Re-usability (FAIR) of data is the last aspect of FAIR data principle. In this regard, data have been and will be published either after the release of the respective deliverables or after the end of the project.

MAELSTROM is making its data publicly available under the Creative Commons Licensing scheme. In particular, the Consortium considers the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial International 4.0 as the most appropriate licensing scheme because while it enables the re-use of data, it ensures that the source and the authority of the data are recognized, and the commercial interests of the participants are protected. In case the needs change along the progress of the project, the licensing scheme that is used might change and the present section will be updated.

In order to safeguard the transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness and accuracy of the data, MAELSTROM applies Quality Assurance and Quality Control activities in the form of peer reviews, data summaries, and input data checks. Data availability after the end of the project depends highly on the type and content of data. Therefore, storing data on a public platform needs to be discussed with the contributor of the data.

Concerning the quantity and the quality of metadata provided in order to enhance data reusability, the ISO19115 standard includes the metadata elements: "Classification", "Use constraints", "Access constraints", "Other constraints" and "Credits". The reuse license is expressed as a human-readable text applying the ISO19139 codelists "MD_ClassificationCode" and "MD_RestrictionCode" (<https://standards.iso.org/iso/19139/resources/gmxCodelists.xml>) within the "MD_Constraints" element (https://wiki.esipfed.org/ISO_Constraints). Dublin Core standard provides a field dedicated to the "license" with dedicated vocabularies (such as the RDF expression of Creative Commons licenses, or the Open Data Rights

Language serializations). Metadata include information about the provenance of the data, such as origin, history and workflow in the Quality section, in particular in the metadata elements Format, Lineage and Process step. The standards used for metadata indicated in the elements Metadata standard name and Metadata standard version are compliant with community standards and machine-understandable. The metadata records are exposed as XML with the HTTP protocol and the CSW allows other infrastructures to automatically harvest them.

8 MAELSTROM Products

Data and products of the MAELSTROM Project are findable and accessible from the project web page “Data management and sharing” at the link: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/about/#datamanagement>.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND SHARING

Figure 2. Data management and sharing webpage of the MAELSTROM Project.

The MAELSTROM Project data infrastructure for managing research data follows the “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020” guides Horizon 2020 that drive beneficiaries to make their research data FAIR (Findable, Accessible Interoperable and Re-usable). The infrastructure meets the FAIR data principles supporting the exchange of scientific data and leading to knowledge discovery and innovation. It consists of four main components:

- 1) NAS repository for research data storage with cloud functionalities;
- 2) Metadata catalogue for research data discovery and preservation;
- 3) RoHub platform for the sharing of the entire research data life cycle and the reuse of scientific results;

- 4) Zenodo, the open repository for EU-funded research outputs from Horizon Europe, Euratom, and earlier Framework Programmes.

Datasets are stored in a NAS-QNAP cloud (<https://qlink.to/GISMARcloud>) based at the CNR-ISMAR in Bologna and described in the CNR-ISMAR Seamap Catalogue (<http://seamap-catalog.data.ismar.cnr.it:8080/geonetwork/maelstrom>). Each dataset is described with a metadata form formatted following the ISO19115 standard for spatial data.

The screenshot shows a metadata form for a dataset titled "MAELSTROM: Microplastics Assessment in Fish, Mussel Farm 2022 (Pre-cleaning Survey)". The form includes a description of the survey, a "Download and links" section with a data link, and an "Other resources" section with a link to the post-cleaning survey. The form is displayed on a web interface with a search bar, navigation buttons, and a sidebar with an overview map and other details.

MAELSTROM: Microplastics Assessment in Fish, Mussel Farm 2022 (Pre-cleaning Survey) Approved

As part of the European MAELSTROM project, microplastic monitoring was carried out to assess the impact of marine cleaning operations. The study focused on two representative sites: Sacca Fisola, within the Venice Lagoon, characterised by high maritime traffic, and Mussel Farm, a coastal area near Cavallino-Jesolo, a former mussel farm.

Both sites were monitored every six months and divided into before and after cleaning activities performed by the Seabed Robotic Cleaning Platform (autumn 2022 and spring 2023 for the Sacca Fisola site and spring 2023 for the Mussel Farm site). This innovative robotic system has been designed to remove macro-litter from the seabed. Among the different matrices analysed, particular attention was paid to the biota, with the study of fish species representative of the North Adriatic area, both lagoon and coastal. The species analysed included mullet (*Liza* sp.), sea bream (*Sparus aurata*), spiny dogfish (*Squalus acanthias*) and sole (*Solea solea*). The main objective was to assess whether the removal of macro plastics from the seabed by the robot was correlated with a reduction in microplastics in the fish themselves, thus contributing to an understanding of the effectiveness of cleaning operations not only on visible debris, but also on the microscopic particles that can be accidentally ingested by these organisms.

Download and links

Data Open link

Tables, protocols and shapefiles
https://www.myqnapcloud.com/smartshare/740724446p705u84397342_90893kk3i378280p1839638x9764ct37

Other resources

MAELSTROM: Microplastics Assessment in Fish, Mussel Farm 2023-2024 (Post-cleaning Survey) Associated resource (Part of seamless database / Experiment)

As part of the European MAELSTROM project, microplastic monitoring was carried out to assess the impact of marine cleaning operations. The study focused on two representative sites: Sacca Fisola, within the Venice Lagoon, characterised by... more...

Overview

Spatial extent

Temporal extent

Creation date
2022-02-22

Provided by

Updated:
3 minutes ago

Figure 3. Metadata form dedicated to a dataset documenting the 2022 pre-cleaning survey, which evaluated microplastics in fish in a mussel farm (<http://libeccio.bo.ismar.cnr.it:8080/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/48529609-9704-42e5-b15b-dbe43f3308f0>).

Through the metadata it is possible to find all the information related to the dataset, download the data and reach related resources. Also points of contact, legal constraints, copyright and acknowledgments are available ensuring the reusability of the resource.

Datasets belonging to the same experiment are organized and published through a Research Object in the RoHub Platform (<https://reliance.rohub.org>).

PUBLIC
MANUAL
LIVE
DATA-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT

APPLIED SCIENCES

MAELSTROM: Marine litter pollution assessment in two Venice demo sites

Susanna Mesghez, Taha Lahami

Contributed by Antonio Petrizzo, Fantina Madricardo, Nicoletta Nesto, Tihana Marceta, Vanessa Moschino
Published by CNR-ISMAR, CNR-ISMAR

Overview
Content
Assessment
Enrichment
Activity
Life cycle
Relations
Impact

An integrated framework has been defined to assess the status of marine ecosystems in the demo site of the lagoon of Venice, including the state of contamination from macro- and micro-litter. The framework is illustrated in Figure 6. Seafloor mapping is used to assess macro-litter presence on the seabottom. Waters and sediments are characterised for the presence of microplastics and microcontaminants. Community state and content of microplastics are assessed for some biological compartments, namely macrozoobenthos and fish.

Ecosystem state and ML pollution assessment: Venice demo sites

☆ 0.00 / 5
💬 0
❤️ 0

0 Downloads
 3 Views

Hide more details

📁 Resources	18
📄 Annotations	103
📅 Events	101
🍴 Forks	0
📷 Snapshots	0
📁 Archives	0
📏 Size	0

AGENTS

Valentina Grande

Creator

Figure 4. Research Object (<https://w3id.org/ro-id/9d238d26-7ebd-4517-974f-f9f91b7055fc>) dedicated to the marine litter pollution assessment into two demo sites to assess the impact of marine cleaning operations performed by using the Seabed Robotic Cleaning Platform.

MAELSTROM Research Objects have a DOI and allow to manage the entire lifecycle of the experiments carried out during the project, ensuring the preservation and the sharing of the project results. Research Objects are also published in the EU Open Research repository Zenodo, where also the project deliverable are available with specific DOIs through the MAELSTROM dedicated community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/maelstrom>).

Published January 26, 2021 | Version v1

Project deliverable Open

D1.1 Set up of project structures

Madriardo, Fantina¹ [Show affiliations](#)

This document summarises the internal organisation of the MAELSTROM project with the objectives to ensure:

- Efficient execution and integration of the project activities;
- Achievement of project deliverables;
- Efficient internal communications within the project;
- Effective dissemination of project activities to the scientific community and general public.

Files

Figure 5. MAELSTROM Project deliverable D1.1 in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/14528560>).

9 Data Security

MAELSTROM ensures easy access to the data and the following guidelines are followed to ensure the security of the data:

- 1) Store data in at least two separate location to avoid loss of data;
- 2) Encrypt data if is deemed necessary by the participating researchers;
- 3) Limit the use of USB flash drivers;
- 4) Label files in a systematically structured way in order to ensure the final dataset coherence;
- 5) The NAS storage offered by CNR-ISMAR to store documents and files guarantee service availability 7 days/week and 24h/day except during blocking incident, after which the service can be re-established within few hours. It ensures also long-term data preservation security.

Ethical issues related to DMP are implemented in close synergy with data management conducted under WP10 (H – Requirements and POPD-Requirement,

respectively). The specific requirements for privacy and personal data protection are dealt with the two Ethics Deliverables of WP10, namely in D10.1 (“H – Requirements No. 1”) - informed consent procedures for the participation of humans, and in D10.2 (“POPD- Requirement No. 2”) – protection of personal data. These documents were prepared in agreement with the document Ethics and Data protection by the European Commission

(https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection_0.pdf).

10 Allocation of resources

The NAS repository and the metadata catalogue used by MAELSTROM for the data management are provided by an in-house marine spatial data infrastructure (MSDI) implemented by ISMAR-CNR during the years in the framework of national, European and international projects. MAELSTROM increased the NAS storage capacity of the MSDI acquiring 56 TB for a cost of 1572 euros. Instead, the RoHub platform is free of charge.

The project members of the General Assembly are responsible of the Data Management of MAELSTROM dataset and research data in accordance with each organization internal Data Protection Officer (DPO). Each partner allocates a percentage of personal cost (person/month) to data management activities, such as data release, metadata filling, and data preparation to be uploaded into European infrastructures (e.g. EMODnet chemistry).

A total budget of 13000 euro is dedicated to the costs related to open-access to research data in Horizon 2020 and are eligible for reimbursement under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grant Agreement. Project beneficiaries are responsible for applying for reimbursement for costs related to making data accessible to others beyond the Consortium. The costs for making data FAIR includes the fees associated with the publication of scientific articles containing project’s research data in “Gold” Open access journals. The cost sharing, in case of multiple authors, shall be decided among the authors on a case-by-case basis.

MAELSTROM

11 Ethical and Legal Aspects

11.1 Commitment to legal aspects

The proposed work in MAELSTROM fully complies with the regulations set out in the GDPR. In addition, MAELSTROM complies with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out. Nothing in this project is deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules, and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

11.2 Commitment to ethical principles

All project partners are obliged by European and national law (GDPR) to protect personal data.

The coordinator of MAELSTROM follows ethical guidelines in its work. Important aspects with respect to this are:

- The ethical guidelines are based on the vision of using science and technology to create a better society and are reviewed continuously to ensure they stay up to date with developments in society and the challenges of today. They generally fall into these categories: research ethics, business ethics, and ethics in interpersonal relationships.
- All partners employees are expected to act in accordance with the ethical guidelines and principles. As coordinator of the project, CNR will ensure that any ethical issues, which may arise, will be handled appropriately and in a transparent and fair manner.

Annex I

MAELSTROM Data policy and License Agreement

Date: 31/10/2023

Authors: Valentina Grande, Fantina Madricardo (CNR-ISMAR)

MAELSTROM Data policy

MAELSTROM Data policy is consistent with, and in the spirit of, national and international policies and laws. Applicable policies or laws are those related to UN conventions, policies of international bodies often within the UN, policies and laws of the European Union. MAELSTROM Data policy is intended to be fully compatible with the Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on public access to environmental information [1], the INSPIRE Directive [2], IOC [3], ICES [4], WMO [5], GCOS [6], GEOSS [7] and CLIVAR [8] data principles. MAELSTROM Data policy is in line with the Grant agreement number 101000832 – MAELSTROM – H2020-FNR-2020/H2020-FNR-2020-1, in particular with Subsection 2 “Rights and obligations related to background” and Subsection 3 “Rights and obligations related to results” regulating the beneficiaries rights and obligations. MAELSTROM makes data available freely and without restriction. “**Freely**” means at no more than the cost of reproduction and delivery, without charge for the data itself. “**Without restriction**” means without discrimination against, for example, individuals, research groups, or nationality. MAELSTROM makes data available in a timely and easy way to users through the data infrastructure described in the Data Management Plan v2 (paragraph 7) and consisting in a cloud repository, a metadata catalogue and the ROhub platform. According to the different types of assets, the **access conditions** vary: 1) metadata are freely accessible without any condition through the metadata catalogue 2) data and products require acceptance of a **license**.

[1] Directive 2003/4/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2003 on public access to environmental information and repealing Council Directive 90/313/EEC (<http://ec.europa.eu/environment/aarhus/index.htm>).

MAELSTROM

[2] INSPIRE Directive for spatial information in the Community (<http://inspire.jrc.it/home.html>)

[3] IOC Data Policy (<http://ioc3.unesco.org/iode/contents.php?id=200>)

[4] ICES Data Policy 2006 (https://www.ices.dk/Datacentre/Data_Policy_2006.pdf)

[5] WMO Resolution 40 (Cg-XII); see <http://www.nws.noaa.gov/im/wmor40.htm>

[6] Implementation plan for the Global Observing System for Climate in support of the UNFCCC, 2004; GCOS – 92, WMO/TD No.1219.

[7] Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS 10-Year Implementation Plan Reference Document (Final Draft) 2005. GEO 204. February 2005.

[8] CLIVAR Initial Implementation Plan, 1998; WCRP No. 103, WMO/TS No. 869, ICPO No. 14. June 1998.

MAELSTROM License Agreement: Terms and Conditions

1. The Licensor grants to the Licensee a non-exclusive and non-transferable license to retrieve and use datasets and products in accordance with this license.
2. Data Users should not give to third parties any MAELSTROM data or product without prior consent from the Data Manager and Project Leader.
3. Data users must respect any and all restrictions on the use or reproduction of data. The use or reproduction of data for commercial purpose must be negotiated and require prior written permission from the data source,
4. Data cannot be used for legal, or for navigational purposes.
5. Data access will be guaranteed through the cloud repository after signing the MAELSTROM data access request form.
6. Data provider can choose to give access to the data with an open license. In this case, the download of data will be guaranteed through the cloud system without signing the MAELSTROM data access request form.
7. Retrieval, by electronic download, and the use of data is free of charge, unless otherwise stipulated.
8. Regardless of whether the data are quality controlled or not, MAELSTROM and the data source do not accept any liability for the correctness and/or appropriate interpretation of the data. Interpretation should follow scientific rules and is always the user's responsibility. Correct and appropriate data interpretation is solely the responsibility of data users.

MAELSTROM

9. Data users are requested to inform the MAELSTROM Data Manager and Project Leader of any problems encountered with MAELSTROM provided data. This feedback will increase the quality of the data.

11. Users must acknowledge data sources. It is not ethical to publish data without proper attribution or co-authorship. Any person foreseeing the use of MAELSTROM data in a publication must communicate with the data source, in particular when the journal requires the availability of data underlying the research findings. In addition, they have to consider the data source(s) for co-authorship of published results.

12. MAELSTROM data and products must be acknowledged using the following citation:
“*MAELSTROM Project - Smart technology for MArinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management - Grant agreement ID: 101000832, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101000832>*”

13. MAELSTROM will invoke legal and technological measures to prevent and penalize copyright infringement.

Annex II

MAELSTROM Data access request form

Name and Surname:

Organization:

Project name and funding organization:

Contact Information:

Data requested:

How will the data be used? (please, provide as much information as possible concerning the purpose behind the data request and foreseen future publications)

Agree to MAELSTROM License Terms and Conditions

Date

Signature

To be sent to: fantina.madricardo@cnr.it; valentina.grande@cnr.it

ANNEX III

MAELSTROM Data Management manual

This manual provides instructions for storing data, adding metadata and sharing the MAELSTROM data.

The MAELSTROM Project data infrastructure consists of three main components, strictly interconnected (Figure 1):

- A **Nas repository** with cloud functionalities for data storage.
- A **metadata catalogue** for research data discovery and preservation.
- The **RoHUB platform** for sharing the entire research data life cycle and allowing the reuse of the scientific results.

Figure 1. MAELSTROM Project data infrastructure schema

The Data Cloud, the Metadata Catalogue and the RoHUB repository can be accessed from the dedicated page in the MAELSTROM web site: <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/about/#datamanagement> (Figure 2)

DATA MANAGEMENT AND SHARING

The MAELSTROM Project data infrastructure for managing research data follows the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" guides Horizon 2020 that drive beneficiaries to make their research data FAIR (Findable, Accessible Interoperable and Re-usable). The infrastructure meets the FAIR data principles supporting the exchange of scientific data and leading to knowledge discovery and innovation. It consists of three main components:

1. A NAS repository for research data storage with cloud functionalities;
2. A metadata catalogue for research data discovery and preservation;
3. The RoHub platform for the sharing of the entire research data life cycle and the reuse of scientific results.

Figure 2. MAELSTROM data management website

Data Cloud

The data cloud repository, named GISMAR-CLOUD, is hosted in a CNR ISMAR server. It can be reach pressing the "DATA CLOUD" button in <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/about/#datamanagement> (see Figure 2).

The user is asked to provide its Username and Password (Figure 3), as provided by the data manager (mail to valentina.grande@cnr.it for account activation).

Figure 3. GISMAR-CLOUD login.

Once logged in, the user can find the MAELSTROM repository under File Station. It is structured in as many subfolders as there WPs are (Figure 4). In its turn, each WP subfolder can contain a folder for each deliverable.

The idea is to associate the Deliverable to the data that were used to produce it (see the following table for the list of the deliverables). Inside a Deliverable folder, user can put all the data concerning that deliverable.

Figure 4. MAELSTROM repository, structured in WPs subfolders.

Table 1. MAELSTROM repository: list of the Deliverables and associated Tasks

Deliverable number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	WP	Related Tasks
D1.1	Set up of project structures	1- CNR	WP1	T1.1, T1.2, T1.3
D1.2	MAELSTROM Project Handbook	1- CNR	WP1	T1.1, T1.2, T1.3
D1.3	Risk Management Plan	1- CNR	WP1	T1.1, T1.2
D1.4	Data Management Plan and Quality Assurance Plan	1- CNR	WP1	T1.1, T1.2
D1.5	Data Management Plan 2	1- CNR	WP1	T1.1, T1.2
D1.6	Data Management Plan 3	1- CNR	WP1	T1.1, T1.2
D2.1	Report on the characterization of major sources of ML and macro-plastic in the demo sites	1- CNR	WP2	T2.1
D2.2	Report on numerical modelling tools to support MAELSTROM removal activities in the demo sites	2 - Deltares	WP2	T2.2
D2.3	Ecosystem state and ML pollution assessment in the two demo sites (Lagoon of Venice and the Porto region)	10 - CIIMAR	WP2	T2.3, T2.4

Deliverable number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	WP	Related Tasks
D2.4	Impact assessment report in the two demo sites (Lagoon of Venice and the Porto region)	1- CNR	WP2	T2.5, T2.6
D2.5	Integrated assessment of the cleaning operations effectiveness and their impacts	6 - VLPF	WP2	T2.7
D2.6	Guidelines on how to consider ML pollution and remediation in marine spatial planning	6 - VLPF	WP2	T2.8
D3.1	Report on the design and integration of the Automated Seabed Cleaning Platform, including video of a teleoperated Cleaning Operation in a representative environment in Venice.	8 - TECNALIA	WP3	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4
D3.2	Report and video about the Cable robot control with Shared autonomy	14 - CNRS	WP3	T3.3, T3.4, T3.5
D3.3	Preliminary report on the Cable robot autonomous control using Machine learning for litter identification	14 - CNRS	WP3	T3.6
D3.4	Final report on the Cable robot autonomous control using Machine learning for litter identification – after long-term learning	14 - CNRS	WP3	T3.6
D4.1	Report on the preliminary study assessment of the surface/water column Cleaning Device in the Netherlands	2 - Deltares	WP4	T4.1
D4.2	Integrated Feasibility Assessment Report for the implementation of the MAELSTROM Bubble barrier in the Porto region	12 - TGBB	WP4	T4.2
D4.3	Executive Plan for the implementation of the MAELSTROM Bubble barrier in the Porto region	12 - TGBB	WP4	T4.3
D5.1	Report on site identification and installation of the Seabed Cleaning System in Venice	1 - CNR	WP5	T5.1
D5.2	Final report on operation of the Seabed Cleaning System in Venice	11 - ST	WP5	T5.2
D5.3	Report on site identification and installation of the Surface Water Column System in the Porto region	10 - CIIMAR	WP5	T5.3
D5.4	Final Report on operation of the surface and water column	12 - TGBB	WP5	T5.4
D6.1	Creation and operationalisation of the software and hardware tracking platform for ML data mining and sharing	5 - GEES	WP6	T6.1
D6.2	Report and video on the marine debris Ai-driven sorting robot	8 - TECNALIA	WP6	T6.2
D6.3	Report on the marine thermoplastics recycling capabilities	8 - TECNALIA	WP6	T6.3
D6.4	Report on the ML processed through mechanical recycling for hard to recycle plastics and organic wastes	5 - GEES	WP6	T6.4
D6.5	Report on low temperature pyrolysis treatment(s) of collected ML	13 - MAKEEN	WP6	T6.5
D6.6	Report on Market accessibility potential of processed ML	13 - MAKEEN	WP6	T6.6

Deliverable number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	WP	Related Tasks
D6.7	Report on the Lifecycle assessment of the MAELSTROM automatic system and ML processing technologies	8 - TECNALIA	WP6	T6.7
D7.1	Creation and operationalization of a thematic working group on ML and Plastic Strategy	10 - CIIMAR	WP7	T7.1
D7.2	Best Practices Sheets Database	10 - CIIMAR	WP7	T7.2
D7.3	Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions	7 - CIMA	WP7	T7.3
D7.4	Unified Reports on Side-events at the Business2Sea and at the International Venice Boat Show	6 - VLPF	WP7	T7.4
D8.1	Exploitation Plan Issue 1	9 - ALPHA UK	WP8	T8.2
D8.2	Exploitation Plan Issue 2	9 - ALPHA UK	WP8	T8.2
D8.3	Report on Costs- Benefits Analysis Issue 1	9 - ALPHA UK	WP8	T8.1
D8.4	Report on Costs- Benefits Analysis Issue 2	9 - ALPHA UK	WP8	T8.1
D8.5	Public summary on Report on Costs Benefits analysis	9 - ALPHA UK	WP8	T8.1
D8.6	Public summary on the Exploitation Plan	9 - ALPHA UK	WP8	T8.2
D9.1	Plan for Communication and Dissemination	7 - CIMA	WP9	T9.1
D9.2	Final version of Plan for Communication and Dissemination	7 - CIMA	WP9	T 7.3, T9.1, T9.2, T9.3, T9.4, T9.5
D9.3	First Interim communication and dissemination report	7 - CIMA	WP9	T 7.3, T9.1, T9.2, T9.3, T9.4, T9.5
D9.4	Second Interim communication and dissemination report	7 - CIMA	WP9	T 7.3, T9.1, T9.2, T9.3, T9.4, T9.5
D9.5	Final communication and dissemination report	7 - CIMA	WP9	T 7.3, T9.1, T9.2, T9.3, T9.4, T9.5
D10.1	H - Requirement No. 1	1- CNR	WP10	
D10.2	POPD - Requirement No. 2	1- CNR	WP10	
D10.3	EPQ - Requirement No. 3	1- CNR	WP10	
D10.4	M - Requirement No. 4	1- CNR	WP10	

Figure 5. MAELSTROM repository, structured in Deliverables folders and subfolders.

Inside each deliverables directory as many subfolders as needed can be created (Figure 5). The user may not modify some WPs folders/subfolders depending on its permissions. Files and folders names should be most self-explaining as possible. Files can be either uploaded or dragged and dropped as well. Although no specific format or file type are requested, it is good practice to metadata them to provide all the information useful to describe them. To create a link to a file which metadata are to be added to, the user must create a share link, paying attention to select “SmartShare” as Domain name/IP. To keep control over the file distribution, it’s recommended setting a password that will be asked to download the file (Figure 6).

Figure 6. MAELSTROM repository, creating a share link.

Metadata Catalogue

Metadata can be added to the data through a service provided by CNR-ISMAR. It can be reached by pressing the “METADATA CATALOGUE” button in <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/about/#datamanagement> (Figure 2).

User can sign in with the same username and password provided for the Data Cloud service. After logging in, the *contribute* button will be available and the user can *add new records* (Figure 7). The search function is always available, also without logging in.

Figure 7. MAELSTROM Metadata Catalogue.

When adding new records, the user must choose a template and then is asked to provide all the information for filling the file metadata (Figure 8). The original resource can be linked to the metadata adding it as “Associated resources - online resources” using the sharable link obtained in the Data Cloud. It is to be noted that different resources can be linked.

Figure 8. MAELSTROM Metadata Catalogue, creating record.

In Figure 9 is shown an example of a metadata record.

The screenshot displays a metadata record in the MAELSTROM Metadata Catalogue. The record is titled "MAELSTROM: Sacca Fisola 2022 November Bathymetry" and is currently in an "On going" state. The description states: "Data collected in November 2022 by CNR- ISMAR VE within the MAELSTROM project with the aim to map marine litter on the seafloor".

The record includes several sections:

- Download and links:**
 - "Automatic detection of MLs targets from the bathymetry" (Research Object in ROHub with DOI: <https://n3id.org/ro-id/9e5d1919-6462-41e1-a4ad-b9e1140925ca>)
 - "Sacca Fisola 2022 November Bathymetry (MAELSTROM Project)" (http://gismarcloud.myqnapcloud.com:8080/share.cgi?ssid=4e13b5e58da42ad825c900b44024ca7)
- Associated resources:**
 - "MAELSTROM Project - Smart technology for MAriNE Litter Sustainable RemOval and Management" (Parent record)
 - "MAELSTROM: Mussel Farm 2022 Bathymetry" (Associated resource)
 - "MAELSTROM: Mussel Farm 2022 February Microplastics fish samples" (Associated resource)
- Overview:** Includes a 3D bathymetry map of the area.
- Spatial extent:** "mediterranean sea; eastern basin; adriatic sea" with a map showing the "Laguna di Venezia".
- Temporal extent:** "Creation date: 2023-02-09".
- Period:** "Provided by" with the CNR-ISMAR logo.

Figure 9. MAELSTROM Metadata Catalogue, example of metadata record.

RoHUB Repository

According to the FAIR principles, the creation and dissemination of Research Objects (ROs) are suggested. ROs are useful instruments for:

- organizing and describing the resources, materials, and methods of an investigation.
- sharing research materials with other scientists at discrete milestones, uniquely identifying them by an a DOI (RO as a social object).
- facilitating the reproducibility and reuse of scientific methods.
- being recognized and cited (even constituent parts).
- preserving results and prevent decay (curation of workflow definition; using provenance for partial rerun).
- providing evidence to findings claimed in scholarly articles.

A dedicated service was developed within the Horizon 2020 Reliance Project (<https://www.reliance-project.eu>). This service allows the community to create and share ROs.

The website is reachable pressing the "ROHUB REPOSITORY" button in <https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/about/#datamanagement> (Figure 2).

User must first sign up or sign in and then will be allowed to create new ROs (Figure 10). When a new RO is going to be created, several information is needed to be provided. The user is guided through this process

(Figure 11). More information can be found at <https://reliance-eosc.github.io/rohub-portal-documentation>. An example of RO is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 10. RoHUB Repository.

Figure 11. RoHUB Repository, creating new RO.

Created: 19.09.2023 (22:25), last modified: 26.09.2023 (17:57)

PUBLIC **MANUAL** **LIVE** **WORKFLOW-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT** **MAELSTROM PROJECT** **ARCGIS TOOL SKETCH**

APPLIED SCIENCES
Automatic detection of MLs targets from the bathymetry
 Antonio Petrizzo, Fantina Madricardo, Vanessa Moschino

Contributed by: Valentina Grande
 Published by: CNR-ISMAR

Overview Content Assessment Enrichment Activity Life cycle Relations Impact

A dedicated workflow in ArcGIS (shared as Jupyter notebook) was developed to identify targets from the bathymetry within the MAELSTROM Project - Smart technology for Marine Litter Sustainable Removal and Management. In that framework, the workflow identified marine litter on the seafloor starting from a bathymetric surface collected in Sacca Fisola (Venice Lagoon) on 2021.

40 Downloads **167** Views
 Hide more details

- Resources: 12
- Annotations: 80
- Events: 101
- Forks: 0
- Snapshots: 0
- Archives: 0
- Size: 11513.52 KB

AGENTS
 Valentina Grande
 Creator

COMPLETENESS 100%

KEYWORDS:
 VENICE LAGOON JUPYTER NOTEBOOK ADRIATIC SEA
 BATHYMETRY DETECTION MARINE LITTER GEOPHYSICS
 MARINE POLLUTION

DISCOVERED METADATA:
 HYDROGRAPHY REMOTE SENSING EARTH SCIENCES
 NATURAL SCIENCE MARINE LITTER OCEANS GEOGRAPHY
 INSTRUMENTATION AND PHOTOGRAPHY ENGINEERING
 OIL SPILL VENICE

TOOLBOX
 [Icons for various tools]

SHARE
 [Social media icons]

CITE AS
 Petrizzo, Antonio, Fantina Madricardo, Vanessa Moschino and Valentina Grande. "Automatic detection of MLs targets from the bathymetry". ROHub. Sep 19, 2023. <https://w3id.org/ro-id/058215c9-d7d3-4e78-8f49-5655f999d5e3>.

LOCATION: [Dropdown menu]

CONTENT

- biblio
 - Scientific paper - Semi-automated characterisation of seabed...
 - Research Object - SinkTrack
 - Research Object - SinkVel
 - DELIVERABLE 3.2.1 Report on the experimental results (3650Kb)
 - DELIVERABLE 3.2.2 Research Object with the experiment data a... (710Kb)
 - DELIVERABLE 3.3.1 Report on the survey and elaborated data i... (1707Kb)

ACTIVITY [Dropdown menu]

LIFE CYCLE CHART [Dropdown menu]

SIMILAR ROS [Dropdown menu]

Show All Annotations [Dropdown menu]

Figure 12. RoHUB Repository, RO example.